

Influence of School Climate on Administration of Public Primary Schools in Rivers State for Sustainable Development

Abigail Ebom-Jebose, PhD ✉

Institute of Education, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Abstract

The study investigated influence of school climate on administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development. Three specific objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. This study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 9,033 consisting of 1,012 head teachers and 8,021 primary school teachers. The sample size for the study is 543 (174 headteachers and 369 teachers). The data collecting instrument for this study is a self-structured questionnaire titled “Influence of School Climate on Administration of Public Primary Schools in Rivers State for Sustainable Development Questionnaire” The instrument was structured using 4-point rating scale and was face and content validated by three experts in Measurement and Evaluation in Rivers State University. The instrument was tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha Statistics and the scores collated yielded an average reliability index of 0.84. All the 493 copies of the questionnaire administered were retrieved and used for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance with a critical value of ± 1.96 . Findings revealed that innovative, open, and toxic climates influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development to a high extent. Based on the findings, it was recommended that public primary schools’ administrators should organize regular workshops and training sessions should be provided to help teachers adopt new pedagogical approaches and technologies, school administrators should open channels for feedback should be established, where staff and students feel comfortable voicing concerns or suggestions and school administrators should conduct regular assessments to understand the causes of negativity, such as poor leadership, bullying, or inadequate resources.

Keywords: *School Climate, Administration, Sustainable Development, Innovative, Open, Toxic.*

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Introduction

School climate is a critical factor influencing the effectiveness and efficiency of educational institutions, particularly in public primary schools. It encompasses the physical, social, and academic environments that shape the experiences of students, teachers, and administrators. A positive school climate fosters motivation, enhances academic performance, and improves overall school administration (Cohen, McCabe, Michelli, & Pickeral, 2009). Conversely, a negative school climate can hinder learning processes, lower staff morale, and contribute to administrative inefficiencies.

Public primary schools play a crucial role in shaping the foundation of education and ensuring sustainable development. Sustainable development in education involves creating an inclusive, equitable, and quality learning environment that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to learn and grow (United Nations, 2015). The administration of public primary schools, therefore, requires strategic leadership and management that fosters a conducive school climate to

achieve long-term educational goals. The administration of public primary schools is significantly influenced by school climate. When administrators cultivate a positive school climate, they create a supportive environment for teachers, students, and the broader school community (Hoy & Miskel, 2008). A positive climate enables smooth policy implementation, fosters collaboration, and enhances the decision-making process. A positive school climate contributes to sustainable development by enhancing quality education, promoting equity and inclusion, encourage community participation, and developing leadership skills.

School administration in public primary schools involves the implementation of policies, curriculum management, teacher supervision, student discipline, and resource allocation (Bush, 2011). Effective school administration ensures that schools operate efficiently, uphold academic standards, and create an environment conducive to holistic student development. For education to contribute to sustainable development, school administrators must adopt strategies that promote equity, inclusion, and lifelong learning (UNESCO, 2017). A well-managed school fosters critical thinking, problem-solving, and responsible citizenship, and skills essential for sustainability. Effective school leadership aligns educational goals with broader sustainable development objectives, ensuring that future generations are equipped with knowledge and values that promote economic, social, and environmental well-being (World Bank, 2018).

Innovative climate refers to the organizational culture that promotes innovation, creativity and risk-taking. Numerous studies have investigated the impact of innovative climate on primary school administration. A study by Moolennar, Daly, and Slegers (2010) found that primary schools with a strong innovative climate tend to have better student outcomes, including higher academic achievement and improved social skills. Another study by Daly, Moolennar, and Slegers (2010) discovered that innovative climate is positively related to teacher job satisfaction and commitment.

Open climate refers to an organizational culture characterized by openness, transparency, and free-flowing communication. Hoy and Miskey (2008) opined that in primary school administration, an open climate can have a significant impact on teacher morale, student outcomes, and overall school effectiveness.

Toxic climate refers to a negative and unhealthy organizational culture that can lead to decreased morale, motivation, and productivity among employees. Hoy and Miskey (2008) averred that in primary school administration, a toxic climate can have severe consequences on teacher well-being, student outcomes, and overall school effectiveness.

Statement of the Problem

The effective administration of public primary schools is crucial for achieving quality education and sustainable development. However, many public primary schools face challenges related to poor school climate, which negatively impacts leadership effectiveness, teacher performance, and student outcomes, issues such as inadequate infrastructure, weak leadership, lack of teacher motivation, student indiscipline, and poor stakeholder engagement contribute to administrative inefficiencies and hinder the achievement of educational goals (Cohen, McCabe, Michelli, & Pickeral, 2009).

Despite the increasing recognition of the role of school climate in shaping school effectiveness, many public primary schools continue to struggle with creating an environment conducive to teaching and learning. A negative school climate, characterized by unsafe learning conditions, weak interpersonal relationships, and ineffective communication, often leads to high teacher turnover, low student engagement, and declining academic performance (Hoy & Miskel, 2008). Additionally, ineffective school administration in such environments results in poor resource management, lack of policy implementation, and reduced stakeholder collaboration (Leithwood, Harris, & Hopkins, 2008).

Given the central role of education in sustainable development, it is imperative to understand the extent to which school climate influence the administration of public primary schools. Without a positive school

climate, efforts to improve education quality and equity may remain ineffective. Therefore, this study seeks to examine the relationship between school climate and the administration of public primary schools, identifying key challenges and proposing strategies to foster a conducive learning environment that supports educational sustainability.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to investigate the influence of school climate on administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development. Specifically, the objectives are to:

1. Ascertain the extent to which innovative climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.
2. Examine the extent open climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.
3. Investigate the extent toxic climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.

Research Questions

The following research questions will be answered in this study:

1. To what extent does innovative climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development?
2. To what extent does open climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development?
3. To what extent does toxic climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses will be tested in this study at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of headteachers and teachers on the extent to which innovative climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of headteachers and teachers on the extent to which open climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of headteachers and teachers on the extent to which toxic climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive research survey design. Descriptive method was adopted because it entails the observing and describing of the behaviour of a subject without influencing it (Kothari, 2014). The research work was carried out in Rivers State. The population of the study is 9,033 consisting of 1,012 head teachers and 8,021 primary school teachers (Source: Rivers State Universal Basic Education Board, Department of Planning Research Statistics (PRS) Unit, 2024). The sample size for the study is 543 (174 headteachers and 369 teachers). The study used simple random technique to arrive at the sample size. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured titled: “Influence of School Climate on Administration of Public Primary Schools in Rivers State for Sustainable Development Questionnaire

(ISCAPPSRSSDQ)” on a 4-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE) 4, High Extent (HE) 3, Low Extent (LE) 2 and Very Low Extent (VLE) 1 respectively. The instrument obtained its face and content validity through the judgment of an expert in the Educational Management and another expert in Measurement and Evaluation, validated the applicability and appropriateness of the content and the adequacy of the instrument. Cronbach Alpha reliability method was used which yield a reliability of 0.88, 0.82 and 0.81. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using mean with standard deviation to answer the research questions while hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using z-test. To determine the extent of any item in the questionnaire, a decision rule based on the real limits of numbers was used as follows for 4, 3, 2 and 1 point respectively: 3.50-4.00 (VHE), 2.50-3.49 (HE), 1.50-2.49 (LE) and 0.50-1.49 (VLE). The formulated null hypotheses were rejected when the calculated z-value is greater than or equals to the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and failed to reject null hypotheses when the z-calculated value is less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at .05 level of significance.

Result

Research Question 1: To what extent does innovative climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development?

Table 1. Mean Responses of Headteachers and Teachers on the Extent Innovative Climate Influence Administration of Public Primary Schools in Rivers State for Sustainable Development

S/No	Items	Headteachers		Teachers		Headteachers/teachers Average Mean Set	Decision
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD		
1	Modern teaching methods such as digital learning and project-based learning are utilized in our school	3.32	0.93	3.84	1.03	3.58	VHE
2	Technology is integrated in my school administration and teaching	3.23	0.96	3.96	0.94	3.65	VHE
3	Our headteachers encourage creativity and problem-solving skills among students	3.07	0.98	2.87	1.01	2.97	HE
4	The school administrators organize regular professional development for teachers	3.30	0.94	2.68	0.96	2.99	HE
5	The school administrators’ partners with external organizations for school development	3.44	0.88	2.70	1.02	3.07	HE
	Grand Mean/SD	3.27	0.94	3.21	0.99	3.52	VHE

The result on table 1 revealed that headteachers and teachers agreed to all the questionnaire items with average mean scores of 3.58, 3.65, 2.97, 2.99, and 3.07 with a grand mean of 3.52. This infers that innovative climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development to a very high extent.

Research Question 2: To what extent does open climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development?

Table 2. Mean Responses of Headteachers and Teachers on the Extent Open Climate Influence Administration of Public Primary Schools in Rivers State for Sustainable Development

S/No	Items	Headteachers		Teachers		Headteachers/teachers Average Mean Set	Decision
		\bar{X}	SD	Average Mean Set	SD		
6	There is openness of communication between the headteachers, teachers and the students	3.18	0.90	2.97	1.11	3.08	HE
7	Staff, students and parents participate in decision-making	3.45	0.68	2.93	0.99	3.19	HE
8	Strong teacher-student relationship is based on trust and respect	3.16	0.91	2.55	1.03	2.86	HE
9	There is active parental and community engagement	2.70	1.18	3.50	1.04	3.10	HE
10	There is regular feedback mechanisms for teachers and parents	2.74	1.14	3.09	0.98	2.92	HE
	Grand Mean/SD	3.05	0.96	3.01	1.03	3.03	HE

The result on table 2 revealed that headteachers and teachers agreed to all the questionnaire items with average mean scores of 3.08, 3.19, 2.86, 3.10 and 2.92 with a grand mean of 3.03. This supposes that open climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development to a high extent.

Research Question 3: To what extent does toxic climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development?

Table 3. Mean Responses of Headteachers and Teachers on the Extent Toxic Climate Influence Administration of Public Primary Schools in Rivers State for Sustainable Development

S/No	Items	Headteachers		Teachers		Headteachers/teachers Average Mean Set	Decision
		\bar{X}	SD	Average Mean Set	SD		
11	Poor leadership influences school administration	3.27	0.92	2.84	0.98	3.06	HE
12	Frequent cases of bullying among the staff influences school administration	3.10	0.97	2.80	1.04	2.95	HE
13	Unfair treatment of teachers and students influences school administration	3.25	0.93	2.76	0.93	3.06	HE
14	Lack of parental involvement and support influences school administration	3.44	1.05	3.78	1.02	3.61	VHE
15	Limited communications and transparency in school policies influences school administration	3.31	1.09	3.94	1.08	3.94	VHE
	Grand Mean/SD	3.27	0.99	3.22	1.01	3.32	HE

The result on table 3 revealed that headteachers and teachers agreed to all the questionnaire items with average mean scores of 3.06, 2.95, 3.06, 3.61, and 3.94 with a grand mean of 3.32. This implies that toxic climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development to a high extent.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of headteachers and teachers on the extent to which innovative climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.

Table 4. z-Test Analysis on the Extent Innovative Climate Influence Administration of Public Primary Schools in Rivers State for Sustainable Development

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	LS	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Headteachers	174	3.27	0.94	491	0.05	0.60	± 1.96	Failed to Reject No Significant Difference
Teachers	319	3.21	0.99					

Table 4 above shows no significant difference in the mean response of headteachers and teachers on the extent to which innovative climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development. The z-calculated value of 0.60 was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 ($0.60 < \pm 1.96$) for degree of freedom of 493 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of headteachers and teachers on the extent to which innovative climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of headteachers and teachers on the extent to which open climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.

Table 5. z-Test Analysis on the Extent Open Climate Influence Administration of Public Primary Schools in Rivers State for Sustainable Development

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	LS	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Headteachers	174	3.05	0.96	491	0.05	0.40	± 1.96	Failed to Reject No Significant Difference
Teachers	319	3.01	1.03					

Table 5 above shows no significant difference in the mean response of headteachers and teachers on the extent to which open climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development. The z-calculated value of 0.40 was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 ($0.40 < \pm 1.96$) for degree of freedom of 493 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of headteachers and teachers on the extent to which open climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of headteachers and teachers on the extent to which toxic climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.

Table 6. z-Test Analysis on the Extent Toxic Climate Influence Administration of Public Primary Schools in Rivers State for Sustainable Development

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	LS	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Headteachers	174	3.27	0.99	491	0.05	0.50	± 1.96	Failed to Reject No Significant Difference
Teachers	319	3.22	1.01					

Table 6 above shows no significant difference in the mean response of headteachers and teachers on the extent to which toxic climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development. The z-calculated value of 0.50 was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 ($0.50 < \pm 1.96$) for degree of freedom of 493 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of headteachers and teachers on the extent to which toxic climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.

Discussion of Findings

The findings to research question 1 which focused on the extent innovative climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development showed a grand mean value of 3.27 for headteachers and 3.21 for teachers. Findings revealed that the respondents agreed to the statements that, modern teaching methods such as digital learning and project-based learning are utilized in our school; technology is integrated in my school administration and teaching; our headteachers encourage creativity and problem-solving skills among students; the school administrators organize regular professional development for teachers and the school administrators' partners with external organizations for school development.

This indicated that both group of respondents; headteachers and teachers to a high extent agreed that innovative climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development. The finding agreed with the findings of Moolennar, Daly, and Slegers (2010) who found that primary schools with a strong innovative climate tend to have better student outcomes, including higher academic achievement and improved social skills.

The findings to research question 2 which focused on the extent open climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development showed a grand mean value of 3.05 for headteachers and 3.01 for teachers. Findings revealed that the respondents agreed to the statements that, there is openness of communication between the headteachers, teachers and the students; staff, students and parents participate in decision-making; strong teacher-student relationship is based on trust and respect; there is active parental and community engagement and there are regular feedback mechanisms for teachers and parents.

This indicated that both group of respondents; headteachers and teachers agreed to a high extent that open climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development. The finding agreed with Hoy and Miskey (2008) who opined that in primary school administration, an open climate can have a significant impact on teacher morale, student outcomes, and overall school effectiveness.

The findings to research question 3 which focused on the extent toxic climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development showed a grand mean value of 3.27 for headteachers and 3.22 for teachers. Findings revealed that the respondents agreed to the statements that, poor leadership influences school administration; frequent cases of bullying among the staff influences school administration; unfair treatment of teachers and students influences school administration; lack of parental involvement and support influences school administration and limited communications and transparency in school policies influences school administration.

This indicated that both group of respondents; headteachers and teachers perceived that perceived that toxic climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development. The finding agreed with Hoy and Miskel (2008) that in primary school administration, a toxic climate can have severe consequences on teacher well-being, student outcomes, and overall school effectiveness.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that school climate such as innovative, open, and toxic climate to a high extent influenced administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development as perceived by headteachers and teachers in public primary schools in Rivers State. There is, therefore, no significant difference in the mean responses of headteachers and teachers in public primary schools in Rivers State on the extent to which innovative, open, and toxic climate influence administration of public primary schools in Rivers State for sustainable development.

1. Public primary schools' administrators should organize regular workshops and training sessions should be provided to help teachers adopt new pedagogical approaches and technologies.
2. School administrators should open channels for feedback should be established, where staff and students feel comfortable voicing concerns or suggestions.
3. School administrators should conduct regular assessments to understand the causes of negativity, such as poor leadership, bullying, or inadequate resources.

References

- Bush, T. (2011). *Theories of educational leadership and management* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Cohen, J., McCabe, E. M., Michelli, N. M., & Pickeral, T. (2009). School climate: Research, policy, teacher education, and practice. *Teachers College Record*, 111(1), 180–213. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016146810911100108>
- Daly, A. J., Moolenaar, N. M., & Slegers, P. J. C. (2010). The relationship between innovative climate and teacher job satisfaction. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 48(6), 731–741. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09578231011079549>
- Hoy, W. K., & Miskel, C. G. (2008). *Educational administration: Theory, research, and practice* (8th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Kothari, B. (2014). *A design research methodology*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4471-5457-1>
- Leithwood, K., Harris, A., & Hopkins, D. (2008). Seven strong claims about successful school leadership. *School Leadership & Management*, 28(1), 27–42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632430701800060>
- Moolenaar, N. M., Daly, A. J., & Slegers, P. J. C. (2010). Ties with potential: Social network structure and innovative climate in Dutch schools. *Teachers College Record*, 112(9), 198–225.
- UNESCO. (2017). *Education for sustainable development goals: Learning objectives*. UNESCO Publishing.
- United Nations. (2015). *Transforming our world: The 2030 agenda for sustainable development*. UN Publishing.
- World Bank. (2018). *Learning to realize education's promise: World development report 2018*. World Bank Group.